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PREDICTIVE IMMUNOLOGICAL MARKERS IN COLORECTAL CANCER DETECTION

*Bayramova N.,
Dashdamirova G.,
Rahimova R.,
Vahabova G.*

*Biochemistry Department
Azerbaijan Medical University*

ABSTRACT

Recently, immune mechanisms in the pathogenesis of colorectal cancer have been the focus of special attention and are widely studied. Cytokines and antimicrobial peptides (AMP) play an important regulatory role in immune mechanisms. According to the results of many studies, cytokines play an important role in the monitoring and prognosis of malignant oncological diseases. The concentration of Calprotectin in the blood serum of patients in group II was higher than control limits in 13 patients (92.0%) and lower than control in 1 patient (8.0%) ($\chi=24.27$, $p<0.001$). Based on the obtained results, the concentration of Calprotectin increases statistically reliably by 3.5 times compared to the control group, and the coefficient of the integrity of this difference is $p<0.001$. The average mathematical density of this indicator is 3.42 ± 0.48 pg/ml, the minimum density is 0.7 pg/ml, and the maximum thickness is 6.1 pg/ml.

Keywords: Colorectal cancer, Calprotectin, CEA, antimicrobial peptides.

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is one of the most common cancers in the world. The incidence increases progressively after the age of 50. Its early diagnosis is difficult because of its usually remain asymptomatic. Colon cancer and rectal cancer are often grouped together because they have many features in common. Colorectal cancer is the third most common cancer worldwide, with nearly 1.4 million new cases diagnosed in 2012. The number of new cases of colon and rectum cancer was 40.1 per 100,000 men and women per year. The number of deaths was 14.8 per 100,000 men and women per year. These rates are age-adjusted and based in 2010-2014 cases of deaths. The present studies are made on adenocarcinomas, the most frequent histological type of colon cancer, which accounts for some 98% of all malignancies in the large bowel. The majority of adenocarcinomas occur sporadically (75-85%), but 25-30% of the patients have a family history of cancer. In about 5% of the CRC patients, an inherited germline gene defect is confirmed. The prognosis of CRC differs widely among patients, and depends on a number of factors. Currently, the gold standard of prognostication is the clinicopathological staging based on the TNM classification system. Stage of the disease at presentation has profound effect on the prognosis. Prognosis also differs between patients within the same TNM stage, and many clinical, histopathological and biomolecular markers have potential impact on outcome.

The purpose of this study is to quantify fecal and plasma Calprotectin and CEA levels in colorectal cancer, polyps and control patients and also to analyze the

differences between these groups and the diagnostic value of these markers. In addition, we aimed to assess the relationship between clinicopathologic variables for cancer and polyps and fecal and plasma Calprotectin, CEA levels. For working group, plasma samples were taken from 19 controls, 23 polyps, 64 cancer patients and fecal samples were taken from 16 controls, 8 polyps, 8 cancer. Male to female ratio was 30/34 with a mean age of 50 (30-81) for colorectal cancer group and male to female ratio was 10/9 with a mean age of 44 (31-56) for control group. Physical examinations, urinalysis, chest x-rays and abdominal ultrasonographies were performed to all patients in Colorectal cancer group. Blood samples were obtained before any treatment for Cal levels. Blood samples for control group were obtained from the collective of biochemistry department (Azerbaijan Medical University). No local, systemic inflammation or incarceration was observed in control group patients. Patients with normal leukocyte (WBC), C-reactive protein (CRP) values were included in the control group. Age, WBC glucose, aspartate aminotransferase (AST), lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), CRP values of patients who has high plasma amylase and lipase were measured. For measuring plasma Cal values, blood samples were taken to biochemical tube and then aliquots of serum were stored at -80°C for assaying.

Previously the research was focused on different clinical and histopathological factors and a limited number of protein markers, such as CEA. Carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) is a glycoprotein involved in

cell adhesion and found in the blood of some 50% of CRC patients [1, 6]. It is an established prognostic factor and used in clinical practice. Also when analysing subsets of patients (stage I/II), preoperative CEA is reported to be a significant prognostic factor. CEA may rise if recurrence occur, and the reported sensitivity and specificity are 64% and 91%, respectively. Calprotectin (Cal) S-100 is a 36 kD weighing heterodimer belonging to the family of calcium binding proteins, which is composed of light (MRP 8) and heavy (MRP 14) chains. It was first identified as an antimicrobial protein in granules of neutrophils. Cal forms 60% of the total cytosolic protein in neutrophils. Yui et al. found that, the reason for the increase was the migration of leucocyte to the site where an inflammation and tissue disruption occurs. It's released from stimulated neutrophils and monocytes during cell death and cell rupture. It's also found in plasma, urine and various body fluids as dissolved, from as well as in the intestinal fluid and stool [3, 4]. Cal levels in serum and various body fluids can be used as a marker of inflammation. The increase of Calpro in colorectal cancer are shown in many studies. The blood samples were centrifuged for 15 minutes at 3000xg. Serum Cal was determined using Cal ELISA Kit (Cat no: CK-E90177), purchased from Eastbio-pharm (China) following the manufacturer's instructions. The Human Cal ELISA was an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay for the quantitative detection of human Cal. Cal levels were expressed as ng/ml. The limit of detection of Cal was determined to be 20 ng/ml. The intra-assay and inter-assay coefficient variations were <8.1% and <7.6%, respectively. Statistical Analysis in this study, the results of $p < 0.05$ was accepted for the evaluation of significance. Cal values were significantly higher in adenomatous polyps (AP) cases than in control group ($p = 0.001$), value range from 32 to 490 ng/ml. So far, despite many published recommendations to include new prognostic markers, no consensus has been reached to incorporate any of these in the daily routines. The sensitivities of fecal Calpro in CRC was determined. Fecal occult blood test is a noninvasive test to detect low sensitivity for CRC [5, 6]. Colonoscopy is used for diagnosis and it is uncomfortable, expensive and invasive procedure for patients [2, 7]. The results of our study was shown that the increase of calprotectin is effective in the steps of colorectal carcinogenesis.

Fecal supernatants obtained from extraction and plasma samples were determined by ELISA. Plasma Calpro was observed statistically significant difference between control, polyps and cancer patients. Plasma CEA levels were significantly higher in the cancer group than control group ($p = 0.008$) and than polyp

group ($p = 0.012$). There was no difference between plasma Calpro, CEA levels and clinicopathological variables. In the control and cancer group, the differences the area under the curve in ROC curve for plasma CEA, Calpro, 0.728, 0.571, respectively. Between polyps and cancer groups, the differences the area under the curve in ROC curve for plasma CEA, plasma Calprotectin are 0.735, 0.614, respectively. Fecal calprotectin levels were higher in the cancer group than the control group ($p = 0.027$). Fecal calprotectin levels were not observed statistically significant difference between control, polyps patients.

As a result, plasma CEA levels are the unique marker in colorectal cancer. Plasma CEA, calprotectin have value of diagnostic differentiation of colorectal cancer and polyps. Fecal calprotectin may be a new marker for colorectal cancer. In order to increase the diagnostic value of plasma and fecal markers, a large-scale clinical studies are needed.

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